

WPs-2250-2251 CCN10: “DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site”

[D-2B]

RTV HCHO dataset and inter-comparison against similar S-5p/TROPOMI products

[D-5]

Results of the comparison between Skyspec-2D and Pandora-2S HCHO products

Document reference: FRM4DOAS-BO_CCN10_D2B_D5
Document Issue: 1.0
Document Issue date: 20/10/2024
Document authors and affiliations: E. Castelli¹, A. Achilli^{1,3}, E. Papandrea¹, L. Di Liberto¹, F. Cairo¹, M. Valeri²
¹ CNR-ISAC
² Serco Italia S.p.A.
³ University of Bologna

AMENDMENT RECORD SHEET

The Amendment Record Sheet below records the history and issue status of this document.

ISSUE	DATE	REASON
1.0	20/10/2024	Creation of [D-2B] “RTV HCHO dataset and inter-comparisons against similar S-5p/TROPOMI products” and [D-5] “Results of the comparison between Skyspec-2D and Pandora-2S HCHO products” documents of project “WPs-2250-2251: DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site” CCN10

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	3
2. Formaldehyde retrievals from MAX-DOAS measurements at RTV	3
3. Comparison between HCHO tropospheric columns retrieved from MAX-DOAS measurements at RTV and coincident S5-P TROPOMI and Pandora#115 products	7
4. Comparison between HCHO tropospheric columns retrievals from MAX-DOAS measurements at RTV and Pandora #115 products: diurnal behaviour	8
5. Investigating possible differences in Pandora and MAX-DOAS processing	10
6. Conclusions	13
7. References	14
8. Acknowledgment	15

List of Acronyms

ARTOV	Area della Ricerca di TOr Vergata
CCN	Contract Change Notice
CIRAS	Cnr Isac Rome Atmospheric obServatory
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
DEAP	DOAS optimal Estimation Atmospheric Profile retrieval
DOAS	Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy
FOV	Field of View
FRM4DOAS	Fiducial reference Measurements for DOAS
ISAC	Istituto di Scienze dell'Atmosfera e del Clima
LT	Local Time
MAX-DOAS	Multi AXis – DOAS
MPC	Mission Performance Centre
OE	Optimal Estimation
PGN	Pandonia Global Network

FRM4DOAS-BO_CCN10_D2B_D5

QA4EO	Quality Assurance For Earth Observation
RTV	Roma Tor Vergata
S-5P	Sentinel-5 Precursor
SCD	Slant Column Density
SPC	San Pietro Capofiume
SZA	Solar Zenith Angle
TROPOMI	TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument
UV	UltraViolet
VIS	Visible
VCD	Vertical Column Density
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

This document is the report of the activities performed in the frame of WPs 2250-4 and 2251-1 and 2251-2 of the IDEAS-QA4EO WPs-2250-2251 “DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site” CCN10. The WP 2250-4 is centered on the processing of MAX-DOAS SkySpec-2D measurements at Rome Tor Vergata (therein RTV) ISAC-CNR observatory. WPs 2251-1 and 2252-2 aim to compare the MAX-DOAS HCHO products with similar ones from Pandora #115 (located at CNR-ISAC RTV observatory) and co-located Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI HCHO L2 products.

2. Formaldehyde retrievals from MAX-DOAS measurements at RTV

Figure 1: SkySpec-2D at RTV on the roof of the CNR-ISAC building (left panel) and at CIRAS (middle panel) a picture of the ARTOV area from Google Maps is also reported (right panel).

The CNR-ISAC RTV SkySpec-2D instrument is located in the CNR research area at Tor Vergata (ARTOV). Initially (left panel of Fig. 1), the instrument was located on the roof of the CNR-ISAC, mounted on its tripod, quite near the Pandora #115 instrument. This solution was only temporary: there are better solutions than the tripod for performing stable measurements over time. Thus, the instrument was moved at the Cnr Isac Rome Atmospheric obSservatory (CIRAS, right panel of Fig. 1) field on a pylon on a shelter (middle panel of Fig. 1).

The MAX-DOAS acquisition strategy used at RTV (the same as that used at SPC, which complies with FRM4DOAS requirements) is described below. The atmospheric spectra start to be acquired every morning when the SZA becomes lower than 94° (the sun is 4° below the horizon). In the beginning, the SkySpec-2D starts to acquire only zenith-sky spectra. When the SZA becomes lower than 85° , SkySpec-2D starts to perform MAX-DOAS measurements. During MAX-DOAS acquisitions, SkySpec-2D measured in four different azimuth directions: 25° , 90° and 225° and 270° from September 2021 to 27th September 2023, when it was moved to the CIRAS. For each azimuth direction, spectra are acquired at the following elevation angles with respect to the horizon: 1° , 2° , 3° , 5° , 10° , 30° and 90° .

	HCHO UV	Ref. Cross section
Calibration spectral range	337-365 nm	
Retrieval spectral range	337-360 nm	
Considered XS	NO ₂ 298K	From Van Daele [RD-1]
	NO ₂ 220K (orto. To NO ₂ 298K)	From Van Daele [RD-1]
	O ₃ 223K	From Bogumil [RD-2]
	O ₃ 293K (orto. To O ₃ 223K)	From Bogumil [RD-2]
	O ₄	From Hermans [RD-3]
	Ring	Computed according to [RD-4]
	HCHO	Chance and Orphal [RD-5]
	BrO	Wilmouth_et_al [RD-6]
Other fits	Polynomial deg. 5	

FRM4DOAS-BO_CCN10_D2B_D5

	Linear offset order 1	
--	-----------------------	--

Table 1: QDOAS settings for the retrieval of the HCHO SCDs.

Note that Pandora #115 uses the 270° azimuth direction for its MAX-DOAS measurements acquisitions. In this work, we focus on exploiting these observations and consequent products. The MAX-DOAS SkySpec-2D datasets used in this work cover the period from 1 January 2022 to 31 December 2022, and only the 270° azimuth direction is considered. The spectra from the MAX-DOAS scans acquired in the UV region during this period have been processed with the QDOAS software (<https://uv-vis.aeronomie.be/software/QDOAS/>). The QDOAS settings used for this analysis are the same used for the SPC analysis described in [RD-11] and reported here in Table 1 to ease the discussion.

O₄ SCDs are retrieved as well from SkySpec-2D UV spectra. The O₄ and HCHO SCDs are then processed with the DEAP code with the same settings reported in [RD-11]. The HCHO profiles are retrieved at the following altitudes: 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8, 2.0, 2.2, 2.4, 2.6, 2.8, 3.0 km. The retrieved aerosol extinction and HCHO vertical profiles affected by clouds are filtered out according to the color index of the spect Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy ra, as explained in [RD-7].

An example of HCHO profiles retrieved from one day of data (2nd February 2022) and corresponding VCDs are reported in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Example of HCHO profiles as a function of altitude and time (left panel) and VCDs (right panel) on 2 February 2022 at RTV at the azimuth direction of 270°. The grey profiles and dots refer to the filtered data due to cloud screening.

FRM4DOAS-BO_CCN10_D2B_D5

Figure 3: HCHO retrieved at RTV at 270° azimuth as a function of hour of the day and month. The four plots represent the Average VCDs, the number of measurements, the standard deviations and the average error.

The results of the HCHO VCDs retrieved from one year of processing at RTV are summarized in Fig. 3. To obtain VCDs from the profiles, we integrate the values along the vertical range. In Fig. 3, we show the HCHO VCDs as a function of month and hour of the day. As observed at SPC [RD-11], HCHO mean values increase in spring and summer and are lower in autumn and winter. RTV HCHO mean VCDs are slightly higher than the ones observed at SPC. Regarding the diurnal variation, HCHO VCDs generally reach the maximum in the afternoon, except for the summer period when the diurnal variability is lower and high mean values are also observed during the morning. This result was also evident in the HCHO mean VCDs distribution observed at SPC. The number of measurements is almost the same during the year. We recall here that these plots are representative of the azimuth direction 270° only.

3. Comparison between HCHO tropospheric columns retrieved from MAX-DOAS measurements at RTV and coincident S5-P TROPOMI and Pandora#115 products

In this section, we describe the results of the inter-comparison of HCHO at RTV against Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI and Pandora #115 data. For Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI, we used the OFFL v2 HCHO products with quality assurance values (qa_value) higher than 0.75 [RD-8] (similar results have been observed adopting 0.5 as threshold). For this exercise, we used a maximum allowed distance of 20 km (averaging all Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI HCHO products in a circle of radius 20 km around the site) and a maximum temporal mismatch of +/- 15 minutes from Sentinel-5p/TROPOMI overpass. Varying the maximum time mismatch up to +/- 1 hour with a fixed radius, does not cause any relevant difference. The 20 km radius is also used in works such as [RD-8] and [RD-9], while the time intervals used for the inter-comparison may vary. The same temporal co-location criterium was used for Pandora HCHO Tropospheric VCDs data. The Pandora #115 data were available from the 18th of January 2022 onwards.

In Fig. 4, we show the inter-comparison of coincident HCHO VCDs as retrieved from Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI (blue shadow), Pandora #115 (green) and SkySpec-2D (red) measurements for 2022. As can be seen, TROPOMI data have a large spread while Pandora and SkySpec-2D data shows a very similar behavior with SkySpec-2D being slightly higher than Pandora data. The Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI mean difference with respect to SkySpec-2D is about -20 % while it is about 3% against Pandora #115. We recall here that the Pandora instruments are considered by the Sentinel-5P Mission Performance Centre (MPC) as the reference for the validation of HCHO TROPOMI total column, while the MAX-DOAS for the validation of HCHO Tropospheric columns.

FRM4DOAS-BO_CCN10_D2B_D5

Figure 4: Results of the inter-comparison of co-located HCHO VCDs retrieved from Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI ($qa_value > 0.75$), Pandora #115 and SkySpec-2D (top panel). Differences of Pandora #115 vs Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI and SkySpec-2D vs Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI in absolute (middle panel) and relative values (bottom panel). See text for details.

4. Comparison between HCHO tropospheric columns retrievals from MAX-DOAS measurements at RTV and Pandora #115 products: diurnal behaviour

In the previous section, we compared Pandora and SkySpec-2D HCHO tropospheric VCDs in relation to Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI VCDs. This approach means that, due to the TROPOMI overpass around 13:30 LT, only data around this time are used for the inter-comparison. However, Pandora#115 and SkySpec-2D perform measurements during the whole day and the differences we found in coincidence with satellite overpasses could not be considered fully representative of the entire day. Therefore, an inter-comparison of the diurnal behavior of the

FRM4DOAS-BO_CCN10_D2B_D5

products retrieved by the two ground-based instruments was performed. To simplify the inter-comparison, all measurements in 15 minutes intervals are averaged together.

In Fig. 5, we reported a first example of the inter-comparison of Pandora #115 and SkySpec-2D tropospheric HCHO VCDs for the 2nd of February 2022. The first consideration we made is that the daily behavior observed by the two instruments is quite similar with lower values in the morning and an increase of HCHO values going towards the afternoon. On the other hand, we observed that the bias between the two instruments is about 50% difference.

Figure 5: Comparison of SkySpec-2D and Pandora HCHO Tropospheric VCDs on the 2nd of February 2022.

A second example that refers to the 20th of July 2022 is reported in Fig. 6. Also in this case, Pandora and SkySpec-2D data exhibit a similar behavior during the day. Furthermore, in the morning up to 12 AM, the values of the two instruments are consistent with SkySpec-2D values still slightly higher. In the afternoon the differences with SkySpec-2D start to increase, showing consistently higher than Pandora.

FRM4DOAS-BO_CCN10_D2B_D5

Figure 6: Comparison of SkySpec-2D and Pandora HCHO Tropospheric VCDs on the 20th of July 2022.

5. Investigating possible differences in Pandora and MAX-DOAS processing

Given the differences between Pandora and MAX-DOAS data observed in the previous sections, we tried to investigate the possible origin of these discrepancies.

First, we investigated the differences in the observation geometries between the two instruments. As said, the SkySpec-2D measurements are performed at 1°, 2°, 3°, 5°, 10°, 30° and 90° elevations. The SkySpec-2D FOV is 0.3°. Pandora has a FOV of about 1.5° and performs measurements at 2°, 15°, 30° and 90°. In addition, the processing of the measurements is different: as said, we used the OE-based DEAP code that exploits SCDs of O₄ and HCHO at all the measured elevation angles, while Pandora has a different approach using only angles at 15° and 90°. Due to the availability on the PGN website (<https://data.pandonia-global-network.org/Rome-ISAC/Pandora115s1/>) of Pandora SCDs in addition to Level 2 files, we can use

the Pandora SCDs and the DEAP code to understand the possible impact of a different retrieval approach.

In Fig. 7, we reported the results of the retrieval of Pandora #115 SCDs at 2°, 15°, 30° with the DEAP code for the 2nd of February 2022 (left panels). To ease the inter-comparison, we also reported (right panels) the same results exploiting SkySpec-2D measurements (as in Fig. 2).

Figure 7: Inter-comparison of Pandora #115 (left panels) and SkySpec-2D (right panels) retrieved HCHO profiles (upper panels) and Tropospheric VCDs (lower panels) on the 2nd of February 2022.

As can be seen, a similar profiles shape during the day can be observed (please pay attention to the fact that the scale is slightly different with higher values for SkySpec-2D) apart from the very end of the measurement day. The corresponding Pandora VCDs show more oscillations and lower values, especially in the afternoon. This simple test gives an interesting indication of the fact that the lower Pandora HCHO VCDs are not due to the retrieval code used.

Then, we moved to the analysis of the possible differences in HCHO SCDs measured by Pandora #115 and Skyspec-2D. HCHO SCDs of both instruments for the 2nd of February 2022 are reported

FRM4DOAS-BO_CCN10_D2B_D5

in Fig. 8 (Pandora on the left and SkySpec-2D on the right). For a specific elevation, Pandora SCDs are more variable than the SkySpec-2D ones. In particular, at the beginning and end of the day the Pandora SCDs show much more and higher oscillations than the SkySpec-2D ones. The SCDs of both instruments at 30° are very similar, while the Pandora ones at 2° are lower than the SkySpec-2D ones. The intermediate SCDs are measured at 15° for Pandora and at 10° for SkySpec-2D and they are not directly comparable.

Figure 8: Inter-comparison of HCHO Pandora (left) and SkySpec-2D (right) SCDs on the 2nd of February 2022.

Figure 9: Comparison of Pandora official HCHO SCDs (left) and Pandora HCHO SCDs calculated with QDOAS starting from Pandora spectra (right) on the 2nd of February 2022.

To further investigate the oscillations at the end of the day in Pandora SCDs, we processed the Pandora spectra (available on the PGN website) with the QDOAS code in order to obtain HCHO SCDs. HCHO SCDs, with respect to NO₂ and O₄ SCDs, are more sensitive to used processing set-up (e.g. interferent species such as BrO, used cross sections, polynomial order). The result of our analysis is reported in Fig. 9. Quite similar results are obtained with respect to official Pandora SCDs, with oscillations still present at the end of the day. The fit analysis shows that these oscillations are highly probably due to noisy/low spectra.

6. Conclusions

This report describes the one-year HCHO dataset retrieved from UV spectra measured by the MAX-DOAS SkySpec-2D system in RTV. The dataset covers the period from 1 January 2022 to 31 December 2022 and, in particular, the azimuth observing direction at 270°. HCHO Tropospheric VCDs at RTV increase in spring and summer, and they are lower in autumn and winter (similarly to those observed in SPC), with maximum values in the afternoon towards the end of the measurement day. The seasonal behavior observed at RTV is in line with the typical climatology of this gas.

The inter-comparison against co-located Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI and Pandora HCHO products was performed. The co-location criteria adopted for the inter-comparison is a 20 km radius around the RTV site and 15 minutes before and after the Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI overpass (around 13:30 LT). This exercise highlighted a mean difference of -20% of Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI products against the SkySpec-2D ones and of about 3% against Pandora #115. The bias against SkySpec-2D is similar but slightly higher in absolute values than at SPC, around -15%. In any case, both biases are within the Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI mission requirements (80%) as in [RD-10].

In the second part of this study, we also deepened the results of the inter-comparison with co-located Pandora #115 HCHO Tropospheric VCDs. The HCHO Tropospheric VCDs are retrieved from MAX-DOAS Pandora #115 scans performed at 270° azimuth. The inter-comparison with SkySpec-2D ones revealed the same observed behavior during the day but with lower Pandora values, especially in the second part of the day (bias from -50% in winter to -17% in summer with respect to the SkySpec-2D).

To further investigate the possible origin of this bias, we processed the Pandora SCDs with our retrieval code (DEAP), highlighting that the differences are not due to the retrieval codes adopted. Looking at the SCDs, it seems that the Pandora ones are more oscillating and lower (especially at the end of the measurement day) with respect to the SkySpec-2D ones. Processing the Pandora spectra with the QDOAS software, we obtained SCDs (even if more noisy and slightly higher) similar to the official processing, highlighting that the oscillations observed at the end of the day are due to noisy/low Pandora spectra.

We recall here that the Pandora instruments are considered by the Sentinel-5P MPC as the reference for the validation of HCHO TROPOMI total column, while the MAX-DOAS for the validation of HCHO Tropospheric columns.

Although this investigation has to be considered preliminary and not conclusive, it highlights the value of both Pandora and SkySpec-2D instruments in capturing HCHO Tropospheric VCDs' diurnal variability.

7. References

[RD-1] Vandaele, A.C.; Hermans, C.; Simon, P.C.; Carleer, M.; Colin, R.; Fally, S.; Merienne, M.F.; Jenouvrier, A.; Coquart, B. Measurements of the NO₂ absorption cross-section from 42 000 cm⁻¹ to 10 000 cm⁻¹ (238–1000 nm) at 220 K and 294 K. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer* 1998, 59, 171–184.

[RD-2] Bogumil, K.; Orphal, J.; Homann, T.; Voigt, S.; Spietz, P.; Fleischmann, O.; Vogel, A.; Hartmann, M.; Kromminga, H.; Bovensmann, H.; others. Measurements of molecular absorption spectra with the SCIAMACHY pre-flight model: instrument characterization and reference data for atmospheric remote-sensing in the 230–2380 nm region. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry* 2003, 157, 167–184.

[RD-3] Hermans, C.; Vandaele, A.C.; Carleer, M.; Fally, S.; Colin, R.; Jenouvrier, A.; Coquart, B.; Mérienne, M.F. Absorption cross-sections of atmospheric constituents: NO₂, O₂, and H₂O. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 1999, 6, 151–158.

[RD-4] Wagner, T. Satellite observations of atmospheric halogen oxides; Mensch & Buch, 1999.

[RD-5] K. Chance, J. Orphal, Revised ultraviolet absorption cross sections of H₂CO for the HITRAN database, *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, Volume 112, Issue 9, 2011, Pages 1509-1510, ISSN 0022-4073, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2011.02.002>.

[RD-6] Wilmouth DM, Hanisco TF, Donahue NM, Anderson JG. Fourier transform ultraviolet spectroscopy of the A²₃₌₂-X²₃₌₂ transition of BrO. *J Phys Chem* 1999;103:8935–45.

[RD-7] Valeri M., Castelli E., Pettinari P., Papandrea E., Di Liberto L., Marinoni A., De Cesari S. FRM4DOAS-BO_Phase2_D3: Report on the inter-comparison results between ground-based and satellite measurements. Document Issue: 1.0, 12/05/2023. https://doas.isac.cnr.it/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/FRM4DOAS-BO_Ph2_D3.pdf

[RD-8] De Smedt, I., Pinardi, G., Vigouroux, C., Compernelle, S., Bais, A., Benavent, N., Boersma, F., Chan, K.-L., Donner, S., Eichmann, K.-U., Hedelt, P., Hendrick, F., Irie, H., Kumar, V., Lambert, J.-C., Langerock, B., Lerot, C., Liu, C., Loyola, D., Piders, A., Richter, A., Rivera Cárdenas, C., Romahn, F., Ryan, R. G., Sinha, V., Theys, N., Vlietinck, J., Wagner, T., Wang, T., Yu, H., and Van Roozendaal, M.: Comparative assessment of TROPOMI and OMI formaldehyde observations and

FRM4DOAS-BO_CCN10_D2B_D5

validation against MAX-DOAS network column measurements, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 21, 12561–12593, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-21-12561-2021>, 2021.

[RD-9] Yombo Phaka, R., Merlaud, A., Pinardi, G., Friedrich, M. M., Van Roozendael, M., Müller, J.-F., Stavrou, T., De Smedt, I., Hendrick, F., Dimitropoulou, E., Bopili Mbotia Lepiba, R., Phuku Phuati, E., Djibi, B. L., Jacobs, L., Fayt, C., Mbungu Tsumbu, J.-P., and Mahieu, E.: Ground-based Multi-AXis Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (MAX-DOAS) observations of NO₂ and H₂CO at Kinshasa and comparisons with TROPOMI observations, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 16, 5029–5050, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-16-5029-2023>, 2023.

[RD-10] S5P MPC Product Readme Formaldehyde V02.05.00 Issue 2.6, 2023-07-20- Released.

[RD-11] Castelli, E., Papandrea, E., Achilli, A., Valeri, M. FRM4DOAS-BO_CCN10_D2A: San Pietro Capofiume HCHO tropospheric profiles and VCDs dataset from SkySpec-2D MAX-DOAS measurements and comparisons with TROPOMI Tropospheric VCDs. Document Issue: 1.0, 30/05/2024.

8. Acknowledgment

The authors gratefully thank the PI(s), support staff and funding for establishing and maintaining the #115 site of the PGN used in this investigation The PGN is a bilateral project supported with funding from NASA and ESA.